

1 **TITLE: Landscape fires disproportionately affect high conservation value temperate peatlands,**
2 **meadows, and deciduous forests, but only under low moisture conditions**

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17 sensing; Polesia

18 **ABSTRACT**

19 Landscape fires are a natural component of the Earth System. However, they are of growing global
20 concern due to climate change exacerbating their multiple impacts on biodiversity, ecosystems,
21 carbon storage, human health, economies, and wider society. Temperate regions are predicted to be
22 at greatest risk of increasing fire activity due to climate change, where fires can seriously impact
23 important ecosystems for biodiversity and carbon storage, such as peatlands and forests. There is
24 insufficient literature on the background prevalence, distribution, and drivers of fires in these regions,
25 especially within Europe, to assess and mitigate their risks. Using a global database of fire patches
26 based on the MODIS FireCCI51 product, we address this knowledge gap by quantifying the current
27 prevalence and size of fires in Polesia, a 150,000 km² area comprising a mosaic of peatland, forest, and
28 agricultural habitats in northern Ukraine and southern Belarus. Between 2001-2019, fires burned
29 31,062 km² of land, and were most frequent in spring and autumn. Although most fires started in
30 agricultural land, fires disproportionately affected natural and semi-natural land cover types,
31 particularly in protected areas. Over one fifth of protected land burned. Coniferous forests were the
32 most common land cover type in protected areas, but fires mostly occurred in meadows, open
33 peatlands (especially fen and transition mires), and native deciduous forests. These land cover types
34 were highly susceptible to fires under low soil moisture conditions, but the risk of fire was low under
35 average or higher soil moisture conditions. Restoring and maintaining natural hydrological regimes
36 could be an effective nature-based solution to increase the resilience of fire-vulnerable ecosystems
37 and support global biodiversity and carbon storage commitments under the United Nations
38 Framework Conventions on Climate Change and Convention on Biological Diversity.

39 **1. INTRODUCTION**

40 Landscape fires, including wildfires and planned fires, are an important component of vegetation
41 dynamics in many ecosystems (Barros et al., 2018; Bowman et al., 2009). During recent decades,
42 changes in fire regime characteristics, such as area burned, size, occurrence, and seasonality, have
43 been noted across the world (Coogan et al., 2019; Hagemann et al., 2021; Hanes et al., 2019; Kasischke
44 et al., 2010; Krikken et al., 2021). Despite their natural functions, unusually large, severe, and/or
45 frequent fires can have adverse ecological effects (Holloway et al., 2020; Le Breton et al., 2022; Li et
46 al., 2022; Ward et al., 2020) and threaten human lives and infrastructure (McWethy et al., 2018).
47 Changes to fire regimes can result in an alteration in the carbon cycle and increased greenhouse gas
48 emissions, with stand-replacing forest fires and fires on peat rich ecosystems, such as bogs and mires,
49 having particularly serious effects (Bourgeau-Chavez et al., 2020; Bowman et al., 2021; Walker et al.,
50 2019). To reduce the risk of damaging fires to people and society, there has been a trend towards fire
51 suppression and exclusion in high-risk environments. It is now recognized that reduction of fire can
52 have detrimental environmental effects on fire-dependent ecosystems (Reilly et al., 2022).
53 Understanding the drivers and characteristics of fire regimes is essential for informing fire and land
54 management decisions aimed at reducing and mitigating fire impacts in the most fire-prone areas.

55 The influence of climate change and human activity on past, current, and future fire regimes is
56 increasingly well understood (Bowman et al., 2009). Our ability to predict how different fire
57 characteristics are likely to change under continued global change has also greatly increased
58 (Boulanger et al., 2014; Goss et al., 2020; Urbieta et al., 2019). Previous studies have linked fine-scale
59 spatial patterns in fire occurrence and the extent of burned area to climate, weather conditions, fuel,
60 soil moisture, topography, and anthropogenic factors (e.g. proximity to roads, fire suppression
61 techniques), their effects varying among different ecosystems (Catry et al., 2009; Chang et al., 2013;
62 McWethy et al., 2018; Vilar et al., 2010). Landscape features, such as vegetation cover and land use,
63 have a major influence on fire characteristics through their effects on fuel type, availability and

64 heterogeneity, moisture, and accessibility (Oliveira et al., 2014; Turetsky et al., 2015). Human-induced
65 land cover changes, such as land abandonment, drainage, and agroforestry, have been found to
66 increase fire hazard and severity (Viedma et al., 2009).

67 In some regions, burned area, and to a lesser degree fire size, have decreased over the past two
68 decades, while extreme fire seasons, characterised by large, severe fires, have been reported for
69 others (Andela et al., 2017; Grünig et al., 2022). Larger fires are often a result of extreme conditions
70 such as higher fuel availability and temperatures that maximise fire intensity, defined as energy
71 released per unit of time (Laurent et al., 2019). They are therefore associated with higher severity,
72 often defined as the ecological change caused by a fire (Haire and McGarigal, 2009; Parks and
73 Abatzoglou, 2020). Containment expenses increase exponentially with fire size, as large fires are more
74 difficult to control. Large fires therefore constitute most of the budget allocated to fire management
75 agencies (Costafreda Aumedes et al., 2015; Juang et al., 2022; Podur and Wotton, 2010). Against a
76 backdrop of economic recession, fire suppression is becoming increasingly difficult worldwide, and
77 fire management budgets are under pressure from the increased risk of large fires as the climate
78 changes. As the wildland-urban interface grows, fires are simultaneously becoming a growing problem
79 for people (Grünig et al., 2022).

80 Landscape fires can also be important for maintaining biodiversity in protected areas and other areas
81 of conservation importance (Barros et al., 2018), through natural processes or as part of active
82 management. However, climate change and anthropogenic degradation may cause fires to have
83 different behaviour and increased detrimental effects than seen in historic fire regimes (Flannigan et
84 al., 2009; Imron et al., 2022). The negative impacts on biodiversity can be severe if the frequency or
85 size of fires reduces capacity for recovery or recolonisation (Eklund et al., 2022; Godfree et al., 2021).
86 They can be particularly problematic in peat-rich ecosystems, where increased nutrient inputs and
87 degradation or combustion of peat can threaten sensitive biodiversity and important carbon storage
88 functions (Datta and Krishnamoorti, 2022; Walker et al., 2019). There are also concerns regarding

89 emissions of pollutants from peatland fires, which can have negative health effects including
90 premature mortality (Kiely et al., 2019, 2021; Lelieveld et al., 2015). These habitats are globally
91 threatened by deforestation, drainage for agriculture, peat extraction, fires, and climate change (Ma
92 et al., 2022; Roucoux et al., 2017; Rowland et al., 2021; Turetsky et al., 2015; van Diggelen et al. 2006).
93 Tailoring management strategies to protect and restore degraded habitats and natural processes
94 could result in ecosystems that are self-regulating and resilient to fires, providing a potentially cost-
95 effective, nature-based solution for addressing multiple societal challenges (Griscom et al., 2017;
96 Regos, 2022; Seddon et al., 2021).

97 The factors underlying fire regimes and impacts remain understudied in Eastern Europe. Eastern
98 Europe is of great importance for conservation and carbon storage, but is predicted to see some of
99 the largest increases in fire activity due to climate change (Senande-Rivera et al., 2022). Polesia
100 encompasses the Belarus–Ukraine border region and western Russia and contains some of Europe’s
101 most pristine peatlands and lowland forests. The river Pripyat, Europe’s last remaining unmodified
102 major river, is located in Polesia, and its vast floodplain habitats are a globally important stopover site
103 for migrating wildfowl and waders (Meissner et al., 2011; Pinchuk et al., 2016). Historically, fires have
104 played an important role in the origin and functioning of Polesia’s natural peatland ecosystems
105 (Dyakonov et al., 2020). However, deforestation, drainage, and climatic changes throughout Europe
106 has resulted in peatlands that are severely declining in coverage and quality. The majority of European
107 peatlands are now classified as having a ‘Poor’ or ‘Bad’ conservation status
108 (<https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/habitats/10145>). Exacerbated by increased anthropogenic ignitions, this
109 has resulted in frequent, severe fires above background natural levels (Kozulin et al., 2018). The
110 effects of large, severe fires can be particularly strong in degraded peatlands, altering vegetation
111 communities, affecting soil carbon, and negatively impacting associated biodiversity (Marcisz et al.,
112 2015; Sutanto et al., 2020; Witte et al., 2011). Consequences for human health of fires around the
113 Chernobyl region of Polesia may be particularly severe, as fires could cause radioactive elements to

114 become mobile, though recent evidence indicates that impacts of fire on radiation maybe more
115 limited than previously thought (Beresford et al. 2021)

116 Efforts exist to expand Polesia's protected areas and restore vulnerable ecosystems, with a focus on
117 enabling natural landscape processes, strengthening biodiversity conservation, and increasing natural
118 resilience. The combination of factors in Polesia offers great potential for determining the patterns
119 and drivers of fires, and how areas of importance for biodiversity conservation and carbon storage are
120 exposed to and interact with fire. We used the global FRY database, based on Moderate Resolution
121 Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) products (Laurent et al., 2018), to perform analysis at the level
122 of individual fire patches at a large spatial scale. We used cloud-based processing to compile a 19-year
123 dataset of fires and environmental variables in Polesia. This study had four main objectives: (1) map
124 the seasonal distribution of large fires and how fire occurrence has changed over time; (2) identify
125 land cover types that are more prone to fires; (3) identify the environmental and human drivers of fire
126 size and occurrence with a particular focus on moisture levels (both surface and soil) in peatlands,
127 floodplain meadows, and deciduous forests; and (4) explore the occurrence and spatial patterns of
128 fires within protected areas to determine whether protected areas help mitigate fires (e.g. by
129 promoting healthy fire-resistant habitats or reduced levels of disturbance) or whether they are more
130 vulnerable than other areas (e.g. due to higher fuel load and continuity, lower fire
131 suppression/management priority).

132 **2. METHODS**

133 **2.1. Study area:**

134 The study area covered 155,880 km² of Polesia in Eastern Europe (Fig. 1). Stretching from Poland to
135 the Russian Federation, Polesia covers the whole of southern Belarus and the majority of northern
136 Ukraine and is centred around the river Pripyat. Polesia is a lowland region with natural land cover
137 consisting of peatlands, deciduous forest, and floodplain ecosystems. Raised bogs are the most
138 widespread open (i.e. non-forested) peatland habitat, covering 4,241 km², while fen and transition

139 mires cover 2,598 km², mostly located in the central region south of the Pripyat (Supplementary
140 Material, Fig. S1). Polesia experiences strong, natural seasonal floods, where large areas of semi-
141 natural meadows, forests and peatlands become inundated in the spring ([Wild Polesia, 2023a](#)). The
142 wetlands are exploited for their natural resources, particularly berries, which are an important
143 economic resource for local communities in summer and autumn ([Wild Polesia, 2023b](#)). Extensive
144 agricultural management of fens as pastures and hay meadows, involving mowing, grazing, and
145 burning, has been carried out for centuries (Bragg and Lindsay, 2003; van Diggelen et al. 2006). Fires
146 are therefore common in spring after dry winters when farmers clear the land before planting, and
147 late summer through autumn after hot summers following the harvest (Hall et al., 2021). Parts of
148 Polesia that are of international importance for biodiversity conservation have been designated
149 UNESCO Biosphere Reserves, Important Bird Areas, Emerald Network, and Ramsar sites ([Wild Polesia,](#)
150 [2023a](#)).

151 Like much of Europe, Polesia has experienced intensive human impact and widespread land cover
152 change. The region is now dominated by large-scale agriculture and coniferous forest plantations that
153 are typically more flammable than the native deciduous forests (Adámek et al., 2018). Drainage for
154 agriculture and commercial forestry has changed the region's hydrological regime, leading to land
155 degradation, and in many cases, abandonment of traditional land uses. These changes have created
156 overgrown, drier landscapes that are more susceptible to fires ([Wild Polesia, 2023c](#)). Since 2014, a
157 series of unusually dry years have been noted, in which the once typical annual flooding event of the
158 Pripyat river has been nearly absent (Meshyk et al., 2021). Parts of the region were contaminated after
159 the Chernobyl disaster, which now encompasses the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, where radioactive
160 contamination is highest and public access and habitation have been restricted. Abandoned forests
161 have been accumulating fuel in the form of dead trees and understory vegetation, and large fires in
162 the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, originating in neighbouring agricultural areas, have received
163 international attention.

164 **2.2. Fire data:**

165 We used FRY, a global database of fire patches, defined as “*groups of adjacent burned pixels with*
166 *temporal coincidence*”, reconstructed from the 250 m² pixel-based MODIS FireCCI51 burned area
167 product (Laurent et al., 2018, p. 2). The pixel burn dates are combined using a ‘flood-fill’ algorithm
168 parameterized by a cut-off value corresponding to the maximum time difference between the burn
169 dates of neighbouring pixels belonging to the same fire patch. The Fire CCI51 data is derived from daily
170 Terra MODIS imagery, but estimates of burn dates may be delayed by several days relative to the
171 true date of burning due to the potential for cloud obscuration during MODIS overpass. We present
172 analyses using a temporal cut-off value of six days, which results in more, but smaller fire patches than
173 larger cut-off values. These data have been extensively validated by authors of the European Space
174 Agency's FireCCI products (Lizundia-Loiola et al., 2020) and the FRY database (Chuvieco et al., 2016;
175 Nogueira Pereira Messias et al., 2016). Although validation of remotely-sensed burned area datasets
176 is challenging, intercomparisons of the Polesia subset of the FRY dataset with the MCD14ML Collection
177 6 active fire product (Giglio et al., 2016) indicated no obvious major false positives resulting from non-
178 fire related land cover changes (e.g. floods, snowmelt, or harvesting) (Roy et al., 2005). The FRY
179 dataset includes fire patch polygons and a set of fire patch ‘functional traits’, including the geolocation
180 of the patch centre, ignition point, and fire patch size (Laurent et al., 2018). We used fire patch data
181 for the period spanning 2001-2019, inclusive. We focus on the larger, and therefore likely more severe,
182 fires >1 km² (Supplementary Material, Fig. S2). Thus, the relatively coarse spatial resolution of the
183 FireCCI51 data is sufficient for our analysis.

184 To explore the post-hoc likelihood of burning (i.e. the probability of a fire occurring over the past 19
185 years), fire patch polygons were converted to a 250 m² grid for each day of the study period, between
186 24/01/2001 and 23/11/2019. Each grid cell for each day, hereafter referred to as a ‘voxel’, represented
187 a potential data point. We included all fire observations in our dataset and sampled non-fire ($n =$
188 1,387,222) observations at a 1:2 ratio of fire to non-fire observations, reducing the dataset to a

189 computationally feasible size. We sampled more non-fire observations to better capture the spatial
190 heterogeneity of the region (Catry et al., 2009; Chang et al., 2013), and ensured an even distribution
191 of voxel centroid coordinates across land cover types. We excluded non-fire observations as potential
192 control points if a fire occurred in that cell within a year prior to the voxel date, as fuel limitations
193 immediately after a burn will limit reburn activity.

194 **2.3. Explanatory variables:**

195 To identify predictors of fire size and occurrence, we gathered data on: (1) land cover type; (2)
196 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI); (3) temperature; (4) rainfall; (5) soil moisture content;
197 (6) travel speed (a measure of accessibility) ; (7) population density; (8) distance to nearest road (a
198 second measure of accessibility); and four fire danger metrics of the European Forest Fire Information
199 System, specifically the (9) Drought Code (DC); (10) Keetch-Byram Drought Index (KBDI); (11) Fire
200 Weather Index (FWI); and (12) Fine Fuel Moisture Code (FFMC). The same (or similar) variables have
201 proved to be important in explaining fires in other areas (see references in Table 1). These data were
202 obtained from existing published datasets (see data sources in Table 1), referenced in full below.
203 Because of the flat and uniform topography of the study region, elevation was not explored. The fire
204 patch polygons and sampled voxels were overlaid onto each pixel-based raster layer. Maximum pixel
205 values for environmental variables (2) to (4) and (9) to (12) were extracted for fire patches assuming
206 that fires are more likely a product of extreme conditions rather than average tendencies (Amiro et
207 al., 2004; James et al. 2017; Turetsky et al., 2004). Minimum values of soil moisture were used to
208 correspond with maximum values of the fire weather indices, indicating extreme drought conditions.
209 Otherwise, mean values were extracted. For the weather [(3) to (4)] and fire weather [(9) to (12)]
210 variables, which are available at daily resolutions, maximum values over the lifetime of the fire were
211 extracted. Input raster layers were resampled to a 250 m² resolution. We used the ‘rgee’ 1.1.3
212 (Gorelick et al., 2017; Tamiminia et al., 2020), ‘raster’ 3.5-15 (Hijmans et al., 2020), and ‘sf’ 1.0-7
213 (Pebesma et al., 2020) packages in R version 4.0.5 (R Development Core Team, 2018), as well as the

214 Google Earth Engine Code Editor, to extract data. We used publicly available remote-sensing and other
215 ready-to-use data products from the Google Earth Engine platform to gather data on variables (2) to
216 (7). The code is available at <https://github.com/btomairekirkland/landscape-fire-analysis>. Complete
217 data were available for 5,338 large fires (82%).

218 We obtained a land cover map for Polesia using the code and method from Dowling and de Jong
219 (2021), which assigns 20 m² pixels to one of 14 land cover types. For analyses, we simplified this map
220 to ten land cover types (Supplementary Material, Fig. S1) and extracted the number of pixels of each
221 land cover type whose centre points were encompassed within the fire patch or voxel. We repeated
222 this for ignition points, including smaller fires. First, we converted ignition point coordinates of each
223 fire patch into 250 m² grid cells. We then intersected ignition points with land cover pixels. The ignition
224 point is the centroid coordinates of all burnt pixels within a patch with the earliest burn date. Where
225 multiple pixels are burning on the earliest burn date and the fire patch forms a concave shape,
226 ignitions may fall outside of fire patches. We used the 39% of ignitions ($n=13,994$) that intersected fire
227 patches.

228 NDVI, an indicator of vegetation vigour or 'greenness', ranging from -1 to 1, was used as a proxy for
229 fuel accumulation (Holsinger et al., 2016; Uyeda et al., 2015). We combined the MODIS 250 m NDVI
230 datasets MOD13Q1 v061 and MYD13Q1 v061 (Didan, 2021a,b), available at 15-day intervals (8-day
231 intervals when combined). We extracted NDVI data from the data product closest in time and prior to
232 the date of the fire and non-fire observations, ensuring the compositing time interval of the image did
233 not overlap with ignition dates. NDVI data were, on average, produced 13 days before fires started,
234 and 95% were produced within 17 days of a fire. We filled in missing data for 6% ($n=418$) of fires,
235 where possible, using the 500 m resolution MOD13A1 and MYD13A1 v061 products, and the 1 km
236 resolution MOD13A2 and MYD13A12 v061 products (Didan, 2021c-f). We collated maximum daily
237 temperature and accumulated daily rainfall from ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020) and mean monthly soil
238 moisture data from the TerraClimate dataset (Abatzoglou et al., 2018). We extracted soil moisture

239 content from the previous month for fire and non-fire observations dated to the beginning of the
240 month (before the 15th), otherwise data from the same month were used. Daily soil moisture content
241 is not available from 2001, but monthly soil moisture data have been shown to predict fire activity
242 with up to two months lead time (Sazib et al., 2022).

243 We obtained spatially co-located daily values of meteorological fire danger metrics, specifically the
244 FFMC, DC, and FWI from the Canadian FWI System (Van Wagner, 1987) and the KBDI (Keetch and
245 Byram, 1968), from the Copernicus Climate Data Store at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>. These
246 variables have been found to be widely applicable in many fire-prone regions of the globe (di Giuseppe
247 et al., 2016). DC and KBDI are indicators of the moisture content of deep compact organic layers, and
248 large dead woody fuels, and provide a good measure of prolonged drying conditions over the previous
249 few months (di Giuseppe et al., 2016; Van Wagner, 1987). FFMC is an indicator of the moisture content
250 of dead fine fuels in the litter layer (e.g. needles, leaves, small twigs), and is a useful indicator of high
251 fire danger in environments dominated by grasses and herbaceous plants (de Groot et al., 2005; de
252 Jong et al., 2016). FWI indicates potential fire intensity if a fire were to occur, by combining the
253 potential rate of fire spread with the potential fuel availability (Van Wagner, 1987).

254 We extracted mean travel speeds (minutes/metre) from the global friction surface of Weiss et al.
255 (2020, 2018), which enumerates the rate at which humans can move between land-based pixels using
256 the optimal path, and population densities (people/km²) from CIESIN (2017). Vector datasets from the
257 Global Roads Inventory Project, available at <https://www.globio.info/>, were used to calculate the
258 shortest straight-line distance from fire ignition points, or voxels, to the nearest road (Meijer et al.,
259 2018).

260 We obtained and mapped protected area boundaries, including Emerald Network sites, using spatial
261 information from the World Database of Protected Areas (UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2022). Unlike
262 nationally designated protected areas such as national parks and reserves, the Emerald Network does
263 not impose a set standard of limitations or restrictions on human activities, but sites are subject to

264 special and flexible management strategies. We intersected protected area boundaries with the fire
265 and land cover data to determine the area and proportion of protected land burned.

266 **2.4. Statistical analysis:**

267 We explored the relationship between explanatory variables and fire size and occurrence through
268 generalised additive models (GAMs). GAMs allow for non-linear relationships between the response
269 and predictor variables and are increasingly used to model spatio-temporal fire processes to quantify
270 ignition risk (Preisler et al., 2004; Vilar et al., 2010) and forecast large fire events (McWethy et al.,
271 2018; Pinto et al., 2020; Preisler et al., 2004). Prior to analysis, population density was log-transformed
272 to achieve an even spread of covariate values, without a few densely populated regions having undue
273 leverage. GAMs were fitted using the R package ‘MGCV’ 1.8–34 (Wood, 2019) in R 4.0.5 (R
274 Development Core Team, 2018). We used a negative binomial distribution, accounting for
275 overdispersion in the response variable, to model fire size, measured as the number of 250 m² grid
276 cells that make up the fire patch. We used a binomial GAM and the gridded fire dataset to explore the
277 drivers of fire occurrence, assigning voxels with a dichotomous response variable, where 1 indicates a
278 fire and 0 indicates no fire. We increased the ‘penalty’ per degree of freedom to reduce overfitting by
279 setting gamma to 1.4 in the model formulas (Wood, 2017).

280 We included spatial locations in the form of centroid coordinates as fixed effects to account for spatial
281 autocorrelation and any missing but important spatially explicit drivers (Preisler et al., 2004; Vilar et
282 al., 2010). We removed data points outside of the main fire seasons (i.e. occurring from December to
283 January or June to July) (Supplementary Material, Fig. S3), which equate to <1% of the total number
284 of fires and burned area. We selected from among the groups of covariates within each model using
285 the double penalty approach outlined by Marra and Wood (2011), which has the effect of shrinking
286 effects to zero, effectively removing them from the model, if justified. Influential variables were
287 identified through visual inspection of plots.

288 Pearson's correlation coefficient revealed strong correlations between DC, KBDI, NDVI, soil moisture,
 289 temperature, and FWI within fire patches (Supplementary Material, Fig. S4). We ran competing
 290 models with different combinations of variables, omitting combinations with collinear variables
 291 ($r > 0.60$), and used the Akaike Information Criterion to compare models. After pre-screening model
 292 variables that best explained fire size, we selected a GAM that included NDVI and temperature. The
 293 final GAM was given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 294 \quad \log(s_i) = & \beta_0 + g_1(\text{Agriculture}_i, \text{Season}) + g_2(\text{Deciduous. forest}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 295 & + g_3(\text{Coniferous. forest}_i, \text{Season}) + g_4(\text{Fen. transition. mires}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 296 & + g_5(\text{Meadows}_i, \text{Season}) + g_6(\text{Raised. bog}_i, \text{Season}) + g_7(\text{Scrub}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 297 & + g_8(\text{Urban}_i, \text{Season}) + g_9(\text{NDVI}_i, \text{Season}) + g_{10}(\text{Temperature}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 298 & + g_{11}(\text{Rainfall}_i, \text{Season}) + g_{12}(\text{Population}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 299 & + g_{13}(\text{Distance}_i, \text{Season}) + g_{14}(\text{FFMC}_i, \text{Season}) + g_{15}(\text{Year}_i, \text{Season}) \\
 300 & + g_{16}(x_i, y_i) + g_{17}(\text{day}) + \beta_1(\text{Season})
 \end{aligned}$$

301 where β_0 is the model intercept; (x_i, y_i) are the centroid coordinates of the fire patch; Year_i is the year
 302 ranging from 2001 to 2019 and was included to explore trends in fire size over time; Agriculture_i ,
 303 $\text{Coniferous. forest}_i$, $\text{Deciduous. forest}_i$, $\text{Fen. transition. mires}_i$, Meadows_i , Raised. bog_i , Scrub_i , and Urban_i
 304 are the proportion of each land cover type within fire patch i ; NDVI_i is the maximum NDVI across the
 305 fire patch; Temperature_i and Rainfall_i are the maximum weather variables across the lifetime of the
 306 fire; Travel_i is the mean travel speed; Population_i is the log of the population density; Distance_i is the
 307 distance to the nearest road from the ignition point; and FFMC_i is the maximum value for the Fine Fuel
 308 Moisture Code, where high values indicate low moisture content. We included a temporal and
 309 seasonal effect as a function of the day of the year. The functions $g_i()$ are the non-parametric smooth
 310 terms describing the non-linear effects of covariates on the log size s_i of fire i . β_1 describes the effect
 311 of the categorical variable Season (i.e. February to May = early; August to November = late).

312 Interactions between covariates and fire season were included, as the effect of covariates on fire size
 313 was expected to vary depending on the time of year (Parisien et al., 2011).

314 Given the potential for restoration of native vegetation and hydrological regimes to promote self-
 315 regulating and fire resilient landscapes, it is important to know how such restoration efforts may
 316 influence fire regimes. Therefore, we specifically modelled the effects of soil and surface vegetation
 317 moisture on fire occurrence in peatlands, meadows, and deciduous forests, while controlling for other
 318 potential drivers,. We used a GAM with the logit of the probability of a fire p_k occurring in voxel k over
 319 the study period given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 320 \text{logit}(p_k) = & \beta_0 + g_1(\text{Meadows}_k) + g_2(\text{Deciduous. forest}_k) + g_3(\text{Fen. transition. mires}_k) \\
 321 & + g_4(\text{Raised. bog}_k) + g_5(\text{Soil. moisture}_k) + g_6(\text{FFMC}_k) + g_7(\text{NDVI}_k) \\
 322 & + g_8(\text{Temperature}_k) + g_9(\text{Rainfall}_k) + g_{10}(\text{Agriculture}_k) \\
 323 & + g_{11}(\text{Meadows}_k, \text{Soil. moisture}_k) + g_{12}(\text{Deciduous. forest}_k, \text{Soil. moisture}_k) \\
 324 & + g_{13}(\text{Fen. transition mires}_k, \text{Soil moisture}_k) \\
 325 & + g_{14}(\text{Raised. bog}_k, \text{Soil. moisture}_k) + g_{15}(\text{Meadows}_k, \text{FFMC}_k) \\
 326 & + g_{16}(\text{Deciduous. forest}_k, \text{FFMC}_k) + g_{17}(\text{Fen. transition. mires}_k, \text{FFMC}_k) \\
 327 & + g_{18}(\text{Raised. bog}_k, \text{FFMC}_k) + g_{19}(x_k, y_k) + \beta_1(\text{Season}) + \beta_2(\text{Protected}_k)
 \end{aligned}$$

328 where Temperature_k , Rainfall_k , NDVI_k , FFMC_k , and Soil.moisture_k in this case are the mean
 329 temperature, total accumulated rainfall, NDVI, and surface vegetation and soil moisture levels,
 330 respectively, in voxel k ; Meadows_k , $\text{Deciduous. forest}_k$, $\text{Fen. transition. mires}_k$, Raised. bogs_k , and
 331 Agriculture_k refer to the proportion of each land cover in voxel k ; (x_k, y_k) are the centroid coordinates
 332 of the voxel. We included soil moisture, as an indicator of drainage and the overall ‘health’ of
 333 peatlands and wetland habitats, and the FFMC, which can reflect the more rapidly changing
 334 condition of non-woody live surface vegetation (e.g. grasses) in addition to dead fine fuels (de Groot
 335 et al., 2005; de Jong et al., 2016). β_2 describes the effect of Protected_k status (i.e. whether the voxel

336 is located within a protected area or not). We assumed fire occurrence was conditionally temporally
337 independent given the fine-scale temporally explicit covariates.

338 To account for the sampling of non-fire observations across land cover types, data points were
339 weighted based on the proportion of the underlying land cover type sampled according to the
340 following:

$$341 \quad W_l = \frac{S_l}{T_l}$$

342 where W_l refers to the weight assigned to all voxels whose centroids overlay land cover type l , S_l is
343 the total number of voxels associated with land cover type l included in our model, and T_l is the total
344 number of voxels associated with land cover type l across our study region.

345 **3. RESULTS**

346 **3.1. Trends and patterns in burned area:**

347 There were 35,954 fires in Polesia in the 19 years between 2001 and 2019, covering 14,758 km². This
348 equates to less than 10% of the study region. Cumulative burned area (counting areas burning more
349 than once) was 31,062 km². The average size of fires was 0.86 km² (Supplementary Material, Fig. S2).
350 There were 6,521 large fires (>1 km²), made up of 669,409 250 m² grid cells, which equates to 18% of
351 individual fires and 84% of cumulative burnt area. Fires were concentrated in central Polesia around
352 the Belarus and Ukraine border (Fig. 1 & Supplementary Material, Fig. S5). The maximum number of
353 fires that occurred in a single grid cell was 11. Data from 2011 onwards indicated that most fires
354 occurred in cells that had not burned in the previous ten years (Supplementary Material, Fig. S6).

355 There was strong year-to-year variability in burned area, with no clear trend over time. The year with
356 the most fires was 2015, when 1,191 large fires burned a total of 4,752 km². This was followed by 2014
357 ($n=950$; 3,803 km²) and 2002 ($n=634$; 2,542 km²). The year with the fewest fires was 2013 ($n=59$; 214
358 km²). The majority of fires occurred in March and April (Supplementary Material, Figs. S3 & S7), which
359 constitutes the core part of the early or spring fire season and accounted for 61% of large fires. The

360 maximum number of large fires for a single month ($n=653$; 2,343 km²) was in March 2015. The largest
361 fire burned for 14 days in March 2003, reaching 204 km², burning mostly protected deciduous forest
362 within Pripyat National Park. Years of high fire activity experienced a second fire season in late summer
363 through to autumn, with 31% of all fires having occurred between August and October
364 (Supplementary Material, Figs. S3 & S7). The longest fire burned for 34 days between September and
365 October of 2015, but only reached 11 km² in size. The wet winter months of December to January had
366 few fires ($n=21$).

367 Almost half (45%) of the area covered by ignitions was agricultural land, which comprised 32% of
368 cumulative area burned by large fires (Table 2). Extensive areas of deciduous forest also burned.
369 However, a relatively small proportion (10%) of the total availability of these two land cover types
370 burned (Fig. 2). Although fen and transition mires made up a relatively small proportion (6%) of burned
371 area, they burned disproportionately more than all other land cover types, with 29% of their total area
372 in the study region having burned (Table 2, Fig. 2). Meadows also burned in large proportions (23%).
373 This land cover type comprised a large proportion of ignitions (19%) and cumulative burned area
374 (20%). Of the fires burning predominantly open peatlands (fens, transition mires, and raised bogs),
375 meadows, and/or deciduous forest, the majority (58%, $n=1,128$) started in agricultural areas and
376 meadows (where low-intensity agricultural practices occur), most starting on intensive agricultural
377 areas. The high fire years of 2002, 2014, and 2015 had greater burned area across most land cover
378 types, particularly fen and transition mires, as well as meadows, raised bogs, and scrub (Fig. 2). These
379 land cover types also experienced shorter intervals between reburns (Supplementary Material, Fig.
380 S6). Coniferous forests make up the second most dominant land cover type, but proportionally little
381 burning of this land cover type was recorded, and it did not exhibit the same increases in burning
382 during high fire years (Table 2, Fig. 2). Urban areas were similar. Patterns of annual burning of land
383 cover types by season are shown in Supplementary Material, Fig. S8.

384 **3.2. Drivers of fire size:**

385 NDVI emerged as having the strongest effect on fire size (Fig. 3e). It had a particularly strong positive
386 effect at higher values (i.e. indicating higher live fuel load). Certain land cover types also showed strong
387 relationships with fire size. The proportion of deciduous forest in the early fire season (February to
388 May) corresponded to fire size in the early fire season, but not in the late season (August to November)
389 (Fig. 3a). Increasing proportions of coniferous forest corresponded to a slight decreasing trend in fire
390 size in the early fire season, but not in the late fire season (Fig. 3b). Intermediate proportions of fen
391 and transition mires were associated with the largest fires in the late fire season (Fig. 3c). A similar
392 peak was observed in the later fire season, but wide confidence intervals make the effect at higher
393 proportions of fen and transition mire unclear (Fig. 3c). Temperature was positively related to fire size
394 in the early fire season (Fig. 3d). Again, there was no clear trend in the late fire season. Initially, travel
395 speed had a similarly positive association with fire size (i.e. the longer it takes people to travel to that
396 location, the larger the fire) in both seasons (Fig. 3f). After travel speeds of ~ 0.015 minutes/metre, its
397 effect was unclear. Distance between the ignition point and nearest road had a positive association
398 with fire size in the early fire season, with no clear effect in the late fire season (Fig. 3g).

399 Overall, fires were of similar sizes in the early and late fire seasons (Supplementary Material, Table
400 S1). The size of fires occurring in the early fire season varied more across years than those in the late
401 fire season, but exhibited a general negative trend through time, and peaked in the high fire year of
402 2002 (Fig. 3h). There was a relatively strong spatial pattern in fire size, indicating hotspots of larger
403 fires along the western and south-eastern borders and the central region of Polesia (Supplementary
404 Material, Fig. S9). Visual inspection of plots suggested remaining covariates had no effect on fire size
405 (Supplementary Material, Fig. S10). The deviance explained by this model was 48%.

406 **3.3. Impact of moisture on the likelihood of fire in peatlands and seasonally-flooded habitats:**

407 Overall, voxels were more likely to burn when the soil and surface vegetation was dry (the latter
408 represented by a high Fine Fuel Moisture Code) (Fig. 4). The effect of soil moisture on the probability
409 of burning was greater than the effect of FFMC. At higher proportions of open peatland habitats (fens,

410 transition mires, and raised bogs), deciduous forest, and meadows, voxels had a larger probability of
411 burning under average FFMC but low soil moisture than under average soil moisture but high FFMC.
412 The effects of the proportion of meadows (Fig. 4a,b) and deciduous forests (Fig. 4c,d) were similar,
413 whereby increasing proportions of each land cover type within a voxel were associated with higher
414 likelihood of burning, particularly under low soil moisture and high FFMC. However, under average or
415 high soil moisture conditions, after the proportion of meadow reached ~75%, the likelihood of a fire
416 began to decrease (Fig. 4a). . There was no clear relationship between the proportion of open
417 peatlands and the probability of burning. However, the burning of large proportions of open peatlands
418 was most likely under low soil moisture conditions (Fig. 4e,g) and high FFMC (Fig. 4f,h). The lowest
419 probability of burning was associated with the highest proportion of open peatlands and higher
420 moisture levels (Fig. 4e-h). The deviance explained by this model was 69.1%. Summary statistics for
421 this model can be found in Supplementary Material, Table S2.

422 **3.4. Impacts on protected areas:**

423 Protected areas covered 19,146 km² (12.3%) of the study region. Over one fifth (21%) of the land
424 within protected areas burned between 2001-2019, covering 3,975 km² (Figs. 1 & S5). This is compared
425 with 8% of unprotected land. Whereas 13% of cells reburned outside of protected areas, 63% of
426 burned protected land burned more than once. The high fire years of 2002, 2014, and 2015 accounted
427 for 79% of cumulative burned area in protected sites. There were no fires within protected areas in
428 2013. Of the top ten largest fires recorded (>90 km²), seven overlapped with protected areas (Fig. 1).
429 This included the largest fire on record, which burned 166 km² of the Pripjat National Park. When
430 comparing national parks and reserves with Emerald Network sites, a roughly equal area was burned,
431 covering 2,777 km² of the former and 3,003 km² of the latter. This equated to a slightly larger
432 proportion of national parks and reserves (24%) compared with Emerald sites (19%). Forests were the
433 dominant habitat in protected areas (54%), predominantly coniferous (33%, Table 2). The majority of
434 burning within protected areas occurred in meadows, which accounted for 34% of cumulative burned

435 area. The most fire-prone land cover types in protected areas were fen and transition mires (42% total
436 cover burned), meadows (39%), and raised bogs (32%). Only a small percentage (6%) of coniferous
437 forest burned. The results of the binomial GAM indicated that the probability of a fire occurring was
438 greater inside protected areas ($\beta=0.598$, $SE=0.008$, $P<0.0001$) (Supplementary Material, Table S2).

439 **4. DISCUSSION**

440 Our study provides important insights into fire extent and drivers of fire occurrence and size in a region
441 of global conservation importance. We show that, in Polesia, fires disproportionately impacted natural
442 and semi-natural open peatlands and floodplain meadows, which burned in larger proportions than
443 other land cover types, and deciduous forests, where the largest fires occurred. However, there was
444 only a high occurrence of fire in these land cover types when moisture levels (in the surface vegetation,
445 but particularly in the soil) were below average. The low frequency of fires in open peatlands under
446 average or higher moisture conditions suggests that peatland restoration, and maintenance of natural
447 hydrological regimes, can provide a nature-based solution to mitigate and adapt to increased fire risk,
448 sequester carbon, and conserve biodiversity. Further wetland drainage and temperature increases
449 and droughts occurring from climate change would likely increase the frequency of large fires, with
450 potentially devastating effects on biodiversity, human health, and climate change mitigation.

451 Most fires started in agricultural areas and spread into adjoining natural and semi-natural habitat,
452 disproportionately affecting Polesia's protected areas. This pattern suggests that habitat
453 fragmentation through agricultural expansion is increasing the vulnerability of Polesia's landscape to
454 fires. Five fires that occurred during our 19-year study period reached >100 km², a threshold often
455 used to classify 'megafires' (Stephens et al., 2014). One fire reached 97 km² and burned significant
456 areas of the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone (Fig. 1) in 2015, which has been shown to have spread
457 radionucleotides across Eastern Europe (Evangelidou et al., 2016). The frequency of large fires in
458 Polesia's protected areas could have serious impacts on regional conservation efforts, greenhouse gas
459 emissions, and human health

460 4.1. Fire occurrence by land cover type and protected areas:

461 Overall, the majority (82%) of the 35,954 ignitions resulted in small burned areas ($\leq 1 \text{ km}^2$). Large fires
462 ($> 1 \text{ km}^2$) predominantly started in, and burned, agricultural land, particularly in the farmlands of
463 eastern Polesia. This is likely both a reflection of the abundance of this land cover type across the
464 region, and the use of fire as a common agricultural tool (Tedim et al., 2022). Although the practice is
465 banned in the region, it is still frequently used. Yet, a smaller proportion of total agricultural land
466 burned compared to other land cover types. This is likely due to fire management aimed at protecting
467 agricultural production, ease of access by fire control services, and the fragmented distribution of fuels
468 in these areas. It may also have to do with the focus on larger, more severe fires and the exclusion of
469 smaller, low-severity agricultural fires, which are less likely to be detected by the MODIS active fire
470 products. Fires were also common in semi-natural, seasonally-inundated meadows, situated along the
471 river Pripyat, much of which is protected within the region's national parks, reserves, and Emerald
472 Network sites. Fires were particularly common in spring, when these habitats are a globally important
473 stopover site for migrating wildfowl and wading birds (Meissner et al., 2011; Pinchuk et al., 2016).
474 Polesia's meadows are characterised by low-intensity agriculture, mainly low-density cattle grazing
475 and hay meadows, where fires are likely started by periodic spring burning by farmers, or accidentally
476 from recreational activities, such as fishing and camping.

477 Nearly half (49%) of the total area covered by fens, transition mires, and raised bogs burned. There
478 was substantial burning in the complex of bogs and mires crossing the Ukraine-Belarus border (Fig. 1),
479 which comprises one of Europe's largest and most pristine transition mire landscapes. These fires
480 endangered globally threatened wildlife, such as the Greater Spotted Eagle (*Clanga clanga*) and
481 Aquatic Warbler (*Acrocephalus paludicola*), and potentially diminished a globally important carbon
482 sink. Due to their conservation importance, peatlands are the most widely protected land cover type
483 in Polesia relative to their prevalence (37%, Table 2). These protected peatlands burned
484 disproportionately more than unprotected peatlands. More than three times as much protected

485 peatland burned (58%) compared with unprotected peatlands (16%). This may reflect lower fire
486 suppression efforts such as fuel management and lower grazing intensity in protected areas. Most bog
487 and fen habitats are to some degree fire-dependent (Flanagan et al., 2020). Fires can facilitate
488 peatland formation (Dyakonov et al., 2020), help to maintain open vegetation (Franks et al., 2018;
489 O'Connor et al., 2020), and enhance overall diversity (Kelly et al., 2023). However, frequent, severe
490 fires can degrade peatlands and create negative feedback loops, making them more fire prone (Nelson
491 et al., 2021). This can result in permanent ecosystem change, threatening sensitive and localised
492 biodiversity (Gosper et al. 2019), and causing increased carbon emissions (Goncharova et al., 2023;
493 Turetsky et al. 2011). We recorded a high proportion of reburning in peatlands affected by fire, adding
494 to evidence that fire resilience of peatlands can be reduced by severe fires (Nelson et al., 2021)

495 Fires were uncommon in deciduous forests, consistent with the known resilience of moist deciduous
496 trees. Despite this, native deciduous forests experienced some of the largest fires. The largest fire
497 recorded during the study period burned 116 km² of deciduous forest, including the old-growth oak
498 and beech forests of Pripyat National Park. Although it is difficult to establish cause-and-effect
499 relationships within complex phenomena such as fires, this likely indicates that only fires exhibiting
500 extreme fire behaviour can spread into these normally moist, relatively fire-resilient forests (Hansen
501 et al., 2021; Hart et al., 2019). The positive relationship between the proportion of deciduous forest
502 burned and fire size during the spring fire season can be attributed to low stand moisture in deciduous
503 forests before leaf flush being more conducive to fire spread (Parisien et al., 2011). Polesia holds some
504 of Europe's last remaining ancient deciduous forest, and the high fuel load and large amounts of dead
505 wood in these unmanaged forests may increase their vulnerability to burning and reduce their
506 effectiveness as fire breaks under extreme fire conditions (Barrett et al., 2016), such as low moisture
507 levels. The emissions associated with large forest fires may be of particular concern, compared with
508 meadow or shrubland fires, as forest fires are larger carbon dioxide sources relative to total burned
509 area (Zheng et al., 2021). These fires likely cause substantial mortality of trees that lack fire-resistant
510 traits, such as beech, both directly (via burning) and indirectly (e.g. through fungal infection) (Maringer

511 et al., 2016). Larger, more intense fires, as well as warmer, drier conditions, have also been linked with
512 reduced capacity for forest regeneration (Flory et al. 2015; Davis et al., 2023).

513 Fires were uncommon and relatively small in the dominant, typically fire-prone coniferous forests
514 (Adámek et al., 2018), which contrasts with other studies. This could reflect effective fire suppression
515 in non-native, coniferous forest plantations. We used land cover data from 2018, so forest fires may
516 have been underestimated if burned forested areas transitioned to scrub or grasslands after fire in
517 previous years (Walker et al., 2019). Furthermore, canopy coverage may have limited the ability to
518 pick up understory fires.

519 We found that under lower moisture levels, indicative of drainage, disturbance, and/or degradation,
520 open peatlands, meadows, and deciduous forests were far more likely to burn. Under high soil
521 moisture levels, peatlands were relatively unlikely to burn. Furthermore, fires burning predominantly
522 fen and transition mires in the early fire season were small, which may be indicative of larger, intact,
523 wetter peatlands in which fires are only able to burn the surface vegetation. The low occurrence of
524 large fires in healthy, wet peatlands indicates that peatland restoration is crucial for protecting these
525 threatened and carbon-storing ecosystems, and promoting landscape-scale resilience.

526 **4.2. Environmental drivers and human interactions with fires:**

527 Higher road and human population densities have been found to be negatively correlated with fire
528 size, which has been attributed to more efficient fire suppression techniques and fuel fragmentation
529 and human infrastructure preventing fires from spreading (Moreira et al., 2010; Pinto et al., 2020;
530 Syphard et al., 2008). Here, we found no effect of population density on fire size, but early fire season
531 ignitions in more remote areas turned into larger fires than those in more accessible areas, indicated
532 by distance to road and travel speed. Land cover type, fuel load (indicated by NDVI), weather, and
533 moisture levels were also important in determining fire size and/or occurrence. The results of this
534 study suggest that drainage for agriculture and climatic changes (Witkowska et al., 2022) could create

535 dry wetlands that are more susceptible to fires. This trend could be exacerbated by a decline in natural
536 and managed grazing by herbivores, leading to overgrown vegetation with higher fuel loads (Mongin,
537 2008).

538 In areas surrounding the Chernobyl disaster, fuel load and type and moisture levels have been found
539 to affect the ability of fires to spread (Evangelidou et al., 2015). Since 1986, 'passive' rewilding in the
540 Chernobyl Exclusion Zone in abandoned land has increased continuity of deciduous forest stands
541 (Dombrovski et al., 2022; Matsala et al., 2021), and it has been proposed that the increase in fuel load
542 has increased the frequency of large fires in contaminated areas (Evangelidou et al., 2014). However,
543 we found that large areas of coniferous forest stands (old plantation forest), meadows, scrub and
544 relatively untransformed agricultural land burned in the exclusion zone (9%, 15%, 20% and 40% of
545 cumulative burned, respectively). In contrast, relatively small areas of deciduous forest, fens,
546 transition mires, and raised bogs burned (5%, 3%, and 6% of cumulative burned area, respectively).

547 The near absence of human interference and the blocking of drainage canals (both intentionally to
548 reduce the spread of radiation, and due to a lack of maintenance and damming by beavers as wildlife
549 has returned) in the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone has resulted in major rewetting and restoration of
550 peatlands (Dombrovski et al., 2022). Former agricultural land has also flooded. Fig. 1 shows that fires
551 were relatively rare around Chernobyl, but were more prevalent in the drier southern and northern
552 tip of the Exclusion Zone. Rising temperatures and increased droughts in coming years around
553 Chernobyl and the region of Polesia as a whole (Senande-Rivera et al., 2022) may increase fire
554 frequency and size in the region. Although higher rainfall in some areas may counteract this effect
555 (see Supplementary Material, Table S2), if more rain leads to vegetation growth and therefore higher
556 fuel loads, it may do the opposite. Large-scale wetland restoration, as is occurring in Chernobyl, could
557 help mitigate the increased risk of fires resulting from climatic changes.

558 The strong spatial effect on fire size and occurrence indicates that there were other spatially explicit
559 variables affecting fires that were not included in the models. Fire suppression strategies are

560 important in determining fire size and their effects can change and mask the effects of environmental
561 risk factors (Ruffault and Mouillot, 2015). The proxies used in our models - human population density,
562 travel speed, and distance to road - may not have accurately captured their effect, especially if there
563 have been any policy changes over time. Another potentially important factor is fire breaks at fire
564 perimeters caused by low productivity land, wetlands, and previous fires (Holsinger et al., 2016; Price
565 et al., 2014). The probability of burning is known to be substantially reduced within the footprint of
566 previous fires due to lower fuel loads, and potentially high moisture content of young, successional
567 forests (Parks et al., 2016, 2015; Walker et al., 2018). This is the negative feedback mechanism that
568 underpins the use of prescribed burning to limit the outbreak of large and severe fires.

569 Little is known about the prevalence, trends, and correlating factors of reburning. As fire rates
570 increase, fires will inevitably begin to intersect with recent fires, termed 'reburning' or 'short-interval
571 fires' (Buma et al., 2020). Intentional regular burning for agricultural purposes may contribute to
572 higher reburning rates and might explain some of the very high fire frequencies observed in Polesia.
573 The self-limiting effect of fires may be lower in fen and transition mires, meadows, and raised bogs,
574 which experienced a greater frequency of reburning than other habitats. The disproportionate
575 number of fires occurring in these land cover types increases the chances of fires reoccurring in a
576 previously burned area. Dried-out, sub-surface peat could also provide fuel for subsequent 'short-
577 interval' fires, or 'zombie' or 'overwintering' fires that smoulder for months or even years (Scholten
578 *et al.*, 2021), as occurred in 2002 around the Chernobyl area (UNCCD, 2019). These fires can have an
579 outsized impact on ecosystem functioning and post-fire recovery due to a lack of adaptation to the
580 increased fire frequency (Walker et al., 2019).

581 **4.3. Greenhouse gas emissions:**

582 Higher temperatures and unpredictable rainfall resulting from climate change may further exacerbate
583 the conditions that drive peatland fires. This could create a dangerous feedback loop, whereby
584 emissions from fires on peatlands make significant contributions to global greenhouse gas emissions.

585 Excluding fires, degraded peatlands already contribute to 4% of global greenhouse gas emissions by
586 microbial oxidation. These emissions are estimated to be 47.3 and 17.7 Mt CO₂e per year in Belarus
587 and Ukraine, respectively (<https://greifswaldmoor.de/global-peatland-database-en.html>; UNEP,
588 2022). The emissions resulting from peatland fires are challenging to quantify but global greenhouse
589 gas emissions from peatland and smouldering fires are estimated to be approximately 500 to 1,000
590 Mt CO₂e per year (Joosten, 2009; Rossi et al., 2016; van der Werf et al., 2017). Smouldering fires emit
591 a relatively high proportion of methane, which has a higher global warming potential than carbon
592 dioxide, compared to 'flaming' fires, with significant implications for climate change (Andreae and
593 Merlet, 2001; Dean et al., 2018). The restoration of degraded peatlands can both reverse their ongoing
594 emissions and reduce the risk of significant emissions from fire events.

595 **4.4. Policy and management recommendations:**

596 The relationship between fuel and soil moisture levels and fire activity indicates that wetland
597 restoration could help maintain normal fire regimes in Polesia. Undrained and intact open peatlands
598 were far more resistant to large fires. Higher moisture conditions in meadows and deciduous forests
599 were also associated with decreased likelihood of burning. Preserving large, healthy peatland systems
600 and restoring the area's hydrological regime (e.g. by blocking of drainage canals) to maintain water
601 levels in wetland habitats may prove vital in creating natural barriers. This could offer a cost-effective
602 nature-based solution to limit the spread and intensity of spring fires (San-Miguel et al., 2020),
603 protecting important ecosystems and their carbon sequestration potential (Kiely et al., 2021; Walesiak
604 et al., 2022).

605 Fragmented, less well-connected peatlands may be more vulnerable to, and at increased risk of, large
606 fires. Drier and more flammable peat might make fire management more difficult in the late fire
607 season, particularly in raised bogs, which are typically drier than fen and transition mires. Expanding
608 and providing higher levels of protection to the current protected area network would create a more
609 resilient, well-connected landscape of healthy wetlands. It would also provide crucial unburnt refugia

610 for wildlife, thereby increasing the resilience of vulnerable species to the immediate effects of fires
611 (Walesiak et al., 2022). The lack of fuel management within protected areas is thought to play an
612 important role in allowing fires to spread (Rodrigues et al., 2023). Landscape restoration provides a
613 means of mitigating damaging fires while simultaneously preserving the conservation value of
614 protected areas.

615 The impacts of increased fire size and frequency in temperate regions, and the degree to which they
616 impact biodiversity, through direct mortality, habitat change or loss, and changes in nutrient fluxes,
617 are still relatively unknown, and require further research. So too does the degree to which species of
618 conservation concern and natural systems rely on regular fires. Rather than advocating for complete
619 fire suppression, we argue that restoration of well-hydrated peatlands would help to reinstate natural,
620 periodic low-intensity fires, providing ecosystem benefits and supporting long-term carbon storage
621 (Davies et al., 2016; Flanagan et al., 2020; Feurdean et al., 2022; Middleton et al. 2009).

622 Updated data on fires from recent years (post-2019) are needed to understand the impacts of war on
623 Polesia's landscapes. The start of the war in Ukraine in early 2022 saw large areas of southern Polesia
624 flooded as dams were removed to protect Kiev against the Russian invasion (e.g. Kramer, 2022), which
625 likely reduced fire risk in the area. However, as the war continues, it will likely impede restoration
626 efforts, and hamper fire suppression efforts directly and indirectly through reduced funding and
627 capacity in both Ukraine and Belarus (Milman, 2022; Rannard, 2022). Active conflict during dry periods
628 could also increase ignition risk.

629 **5. CONCLUSION**

630 Temperate landscapes are predicted to be at greatest risk of fires as the climate changes. Our findings
631 suggest that large fires can be mitigated at a landscape level by preserving and restoring natural
632 ecosystems and hydrological regimes. We found that large fires are driven by fuel load, fuel type,
633 weather, accessibility, and moisture conditions. These fires disproportionately affected Polesia's

634 protected, internationally important peatlands and floodplain meadows, and the most extreme fires
635 threatened ancient deciduous forest. Intact, wet, open peatland habitats are more resilient to fires
636 and could act as barriers to fire spread, but under dry conditions, peatlands are at much greater risk
637 of burning. The reversal of some of the large-scale drainage, undertaken throughout the last century,
638 is likely to produce more favourable conditions to reduce the negative impacts of unusually large,
639 severe fires. We expect that this study, the first of its kind performed in Polesia, will encourage further
640 research into the drivers of fires in other understudied regions to better inform landscape-scale
641 restoration and protection measures.

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Figure 1. Cumulative area burned by large fires (n = 5,388), indicated by a black (single burning event) to yellow gradient, between 2001 and 2019, based on the FireCCI51 burned area product, with lighter colours indicating more frequent burns. Fires are overlaid onto protected areas and Emerald Network sites. The location of the top ten largest fires are also highlighted (represented by the yellow circles). Key locations shown include Kiev, the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant, Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, Almany Mires Nature Reserve (containing one of Europe's largest intact fen and transition mires), Pripjat National Park and Nature Reserve (containing important floodplain meadow and seasonally-flooded primaeval deciduous forest) and Pripjat Stokhid (containing important floodplain meadow and flooded forest habitat).

Figure 2. Proportion of each land cover type burned by large fires annually in Polesia between 2001 and 2019.

Figure 3. Estimated effects of influential covariates on fire size, measured in square kilometres, in the early and late fire season, as determined by a negative binomial generalised additive model. Visual inspection of plots indicated an effect of the proportion of (a) deciduous and (b) coniferous forest and (c) fen and transition mire; (d) temperature; (e) NDVI; (f) travel speed; (g) distance to road; and (h) year, where 5 = 2005, 10 = 2010, and 15 = 2015. The shaded areas represent 95% confidence bands.

Figure 4. GAM results illustrating the effects of (a,b) meadows, (c,d) deciduous forest, and (e-h) peatlands at different levels of soil (left hand panels) and fine fuel (right hand panels) moisture, on the probability of a voxel burning, during Polesia's main fire seasons. Lines are coloured by values of soil moisture and the Fine Fuel Moisture Code. The effects are shown for median, and lower and upper 90% quantile values of moisture levels. Note that high values of FFMC (in red) indicate low moisture levels, and low values (dark blue) indicate high moisture. Shaded areas indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Table 1. Description of input variables used to explain fires in Polesia.

Explanatory variable	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Unit	Range	Data source	Reference
(1) Land cover	20m	N/A	N/A	0 - 1	https://github.com/tpfd/Polesia-Landcover	Catry et al. (2009); Chang et al. (2013); Hantson et al. (2014); McWethy et al. (2018); Syphard et al. (2008)
(2) NDVI	250 - 1 km	~8 days	N/A	-0.05 - 1.00	https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/MODIS_061_MYD13A2	Huang et al. (2020)
Weather						
(3) Temperature	0.25°	Daily	°C	-6.37 - 37.24	https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/ECMWF_ERA5_DAILY	Chang et al. (2013)
(4) Rainfall			mm	0 - 43.85	https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/IDAHO_EPSCOR_TERRACLIMATE	Hantson et al. (2014); McWethy et al. (2018)
(5) Soil moisture	4 km	Monthly	mm	6.90 -114.20	https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/Oxford_MAP_friction_surface_2019	Adámek et al. (2018)
(6) Travel speed	1 km	N/A	minutes/metre	0 - 0.06	https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/CIESIN_GPWv411_GPW_Population_Density?hl=en	Adámek et al. (2018)
(7) Human population density	1 km	5 years	number of people/km ²	0 - 3,836.17	https://www.globio.info/download-grip-dataset	Catry et al. (2009); Hantson et al. (2014); McWethy et al. (2018)
(8) Distance to road	8 km	N/A	km	0 - 10.36		Catry et al. (2009); Chang et al. (2013); Syphard et al. (2008)
Fire danger metrics						
(9) Drought Code	0.25°	Daily	N/A	3.04 - 832.23		Carvalho et al. (2008); Wotton and Martell (2005)
(10) Keetch-Byram Drought Index				0 - 48.90	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cems-fire-historical?tab=overview	Preisler et al. (2008)
(11) Fire Weather Index				0 - 58.09		Carvalho et al. (2008); Perry et al. (2019)
(12) Fine Fuel Moisture Code				20.83 - 96.68		Carvalho et al. (2008); Wotton and Martell (2005)

Table 2. Summary of large fires by land cover types in Polesia between 2001 and 2019. All areas are shown in km². Burned area is defined as the total gridded area that burned at least once during the study period. Cumulative burned area includes all burning during the study period i.e. repeated burning of the same grid cells.

Land cover type	Burned area	Cumulative burned area	Total area of land cover type	Burned area within protected sites	Cumulative burned area in protected sites	Total area within protected sites
Agriculture	5,126	9,960	52,293	394	1,012	1,586
Meadows	2,757	6,128	12,047	1,083	3,034	2,744
Deciduous forest	2,085	3,768	20,382	738	1,397	3,541
Coniferous forest	1,287	2,421	40,760	408	677	6,279
Scrub	1,026	2,036	8,388	313	606	1,241
Fen and transition mire	756	1,715	2,598	460	1,277	1,091
Raised bog	832	1,708	4,241	456	932	1,410
Urban	135	284	5,320	8	92	61
Total	14,015	28,020	143,000	3,860	9,027	17,953

Figure 1

